

Attitude towards E-teaching and its Effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

The present study was made to investigate the Attitude towards E-teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers in Coimbatore. The teachers play the most vital and essential role in the development of the whole educational system. There are many qualities, duties and responsibility for teachers to society development. Because without student or man or teacher there was no exists any society. In the other sense educational development means society development also. Teachers have to teach effectively and motivate their students on the field of education. The study concluded as high school students' level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers was studied and the findings reveal that there is a significant in Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers with respect to Type of School and Locality and not with Gender, Locality and Type of Family.

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Keywords: Customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, service quality, telecom industry

INTRODUCTION

As internet is used widely, it has created many opportunities and applications to support many activities. E-Service is one of them, which include e-Learning. Especially with the concerns about learning and growth concept, many people need to get knowledge as soon as they need. This leads to the importance of e-Learning for developing or enhancing the ability and skills of people, especially in business sectors. That is the reason, why many organizations brought e-Learning to train their employees for ensuring the company's growth. Also e-Learning

helps updating skill fast. However, this study found that it did not guarantee that using e-Learning could enhance skills and capability of all employees. Because of this finding, there are many researches about factors that related to use e-Learning efficiently. Most studies focused on factors that have affected using e-Learning successfully in different environments and purpose. However, based on the limited purpose of using e-Learning to support the learning and growth of the company, it is interesting to study further about how the result of using e-Learning affects the learning and growth indicator of the company. In this study, job satisfaction is chosen to represent learning and growth concept. It also has an effect on other aspects like internal process and customer aspects of Balanced Scorecard concept. The results provide the managers to make right decision for bringing e-Learning to use in their companies. All present, e-Learning is used widely as internet is spread with more and more speed. It provides a new pattern for learning and also it provides more opportunity to learn. It supports continuing learning and self-improvement without interfering with working patterns and life styles, because everyone can access the contents all the time and from every place. For contents, it provides the up to date contents all the time. So it can be considered as an efficient tool to increase working performance and everyone's capability.

In this work, the detail literature, analysis with data collected and the interpretation with its finding are discussed.

Review of Literature

Selvakumar, M. V., & Maran, K. (2019) This research followed descriptive research design. The researcher gathered primary data required for the research through self-administered questionnaire with four sections namely personal details, e-learning courses details, E-learning practices scale, and institutional climate scale.

Kumar, T. S., & Sargunar, V. S. (2019).investigated the integration of e-Learning systems and Knowledge Management technology to improve the capture, online practical classes for rural school students and delivery of both traditional courses and large amount of real-time knowledge.

Haran, V. V., & Jeyaraj, A. (2019).explored the process by which e-mentoring unfolds in organizational settings, emphasizing the crucial role of learning that acts as the intermediate step between mentoring functions and organizational outcomes. The authors conclude with implications for research and practice.

Chopra, G., Madan, P., Jaisingh, P., & Bhaskar, P. (2019).aims to mainly focus on evaluating the effectiveness of the e-

learning experience from students' perceptive. "Survey" method has been used to collect the data with the help of a structured questionnaire from the students who have registered on COURSERA (www.coursera.org/) website for e-learning.

Thangavelu, C., & Kanagasabapathi, J. R. (2019).conducted survey among 300 executives from various passenger vehicles manufacturing automobile organizations located in and around Chennai city.

Subramaniam, R., & Nakkeeran, S. (2019). The results reveal that successful implementation and usage of E-learning systems in software organizations for training employees will enhance the performance of teams even though there are geographically dislocated from one another.

Gupta, M., & Pandey, J. (2018).examined the mediating role of intellectual engagement in the relationship between online engagement and affective learning. The second objective is to investigate the mediating role of academic engagement in the relationship between intellectual engagement and affective learning as well as between online engagement and affective learning.

Maitra, P., & Mani, S. (2017). Overall our findings suggest that vocational education may serve to be a promising avenue through which young women can contribute to their household welfare.

Sehgal, P., Nambudiri, R., & Mishra, S. K. (2017). Results also confirmed that both collaboration and principal leadership are positively related to teacher self-efficacy.

Pradhan, R. K., Jena, L. K., & Singh, S. K. (2017). An examination of the relationship between organizational learning and adaptive performance in Indian manufacturing industries reveals that the relationship is stronger among the executives with high levels of emotional intelligence and weaker for those having low levels of emotional intelligence. Jyoti, J., & Sharma, P. (2017). Evaluates the role of self-efficacy between mentoring and its outcomes namely, relationship quality, communication satisfaction, and personal learning.

Dutta, V., & Sahney, S. (2016). Purpose of this paper is to examine the role of teacher job satisfaction and school climate in mediating the relative effects of principals' instructional and transformational leadership practices on student outcomes.

Variables of the Study

In research, this term refers to the measurable characteristics, qualities, traits or attributes of a particular individual, object or situation being studied. Nurses use the term variable whether they are conducting, reading or using results of qualitative or quantitative research. Researchers often refer to variable by the terms dependent or independent. Dependent variable represent outcomes of interest and they are affect by independent (i.e predictor) variables. In this study, the investigator follows independent variable and dependent variables.

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Male/Female).
- Locality (Rural/Urban)
- Type of School (Government/Private).
- Type of Family (Joint/Nuclear).
- Type of Group (Arts/Science).

Sampling Techniques

The sample which was collected from various colleges located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

**TABLE 1
LIST OF SCHOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION**

S. No	Name of the Colleges	Number of students
1	Government Higher Secondary School, Ganapathy	41
2	Corporation Girls Higher Secondary School, Ramakrishnapuram	57
3	Government Boys High School, Ondipudur	54
4	Sri Ramakrishna Matric Higher Secondary School, Peelamedu	55
5	Alvernia Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Ramanathapuram	59
6	Kovai Kalaimagal Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Siddhapudur	34
	Total	300

**TABLE 2
DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLES BASED ON VARIABLES**

S. No	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1	Gender	Male	135	45	300
		Female	165	55	
2	Locality	Rural	33	11	300
		Urban	267	89	
3	Type of School	Government	152	51	300
		Private	148	49	
4	Type of Family	Joint	89	30	300
		Nuclear	211	70	
5	Type of Group	Arts	132	44	300
		Science	168	56	

Research Tool

Tool become another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. "Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data" the important tools of educational research include interview schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, achievement test, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram. The investigator has used "Effect of ICT Skills on the Job Satisfaction of Teacher Educators: Evidence from the Universities of the Sindh Province of Pakistan., (2016)

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant difference on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Gender.
2. There is no significant difference on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Locality.
3. There is no significant difference on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Type of School.
4. There is no significant difference on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Type of Family.
5. There is no significant difference of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Type of Group.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The following section deals with analysis and interpretation . The table 3-7 address the results of the hypothesis mention in earlier sections and the corresopnfing charts are prepared for thw support.

TABLE 3
Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Gender.

S. No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Male	135	1.4606	298	1.6502	NS
2	Female	165	1.5333			

The Table 3 shows the mean score difference in significant study level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Gender (Male/Female).The calculated t value is statistically high value, a significance at 0.05 to 0.2115 levels and hence the hypotheses 1 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in significant level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Gender.

CHART 1
LEVEL OF STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-TEACHING AND ITS EFFECT ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON THEIR GENDER

Hypotheses: 2

There will not be a significant level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Locality.

TABLE 4
Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Locality.

S. No	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Rural	33	1.1818	298	1.6787	NS
2	Urban	267	1.4906			

CHART 2
LEVEL OF STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-TEACHING AND ITS EFFECT ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON THEIR LOCALITY

TABLE 5
Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students based on their Food Habit.

S. No	Type of School	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Government	152	1.6118	298	1.6500	NS
2	Private	148	1.5405			

CHART 3
LEVEL OF STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-TEACHING AND ITS EFFECT ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF SCHOOL

TABLE 6
Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Type of Family

S. No	Type of Family	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Joint	89	1.5056	298	1.6542	0.5352	NS
2	Nuclear	211	1.5450				

CHART 4
LEVEL OF STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-TEACHING AND ITS EFFECT ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF FAMILY

TABLE 7

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers based on their Type of Group.

S. No	Type of Group	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Arts	132	1.0227	298	1.6512	NS
2	Science	168	1.1310			

CHART 5

LEVEL OF STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS AWARENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AMONG B.ED. COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF GROUP

Summary of the Findings

A study on high school students' level of Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers was studied and the findings reveal that there is no significant in Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers with respect to Locality and Type of Group.

A study on high school students' level of Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers was studied and the findings reveal that there is no significant in Attitude towards E-Teaching and its effect on Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers with respect to Gender, Type of School and Type of Family

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to explore and compare the level of job satisfaction of secondary schoolteachers. The finding of this research show that the secondary school teachers are satisfied with respect to the factors of the job i.e. achievement in the schools, different activities performed, authority in the school, coworkers relations, moral values, responsibility of job, security of job, social service, social status, supervision regarding human relations, supervision regarding technical aspects. The results show that secondary school teachers were not satisfied with compensation, advancement, and policies of education. Satisfaction, dissatisfaction in the job causes success or failure of any system or organization. So, it is pertinent to be aware of the job satisfaction level of secondary school teachers. It may be due to the fact that there are fewer facilities in the rural areas, while in urban areas employees have better job opportunities, high standard educational institutions, and better health and transport facilities. On the basis of conclusion of this study, it is recommended that elementary teachers may be provided with better salary package, rapid promotion, opportunities for creative work, recognition by the department, active participation in policy formulation and better working conditions of the institutions. These

eight aspects may be taken for further study at different sample.

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PERSONAL DATA SHEET APPENDICES PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA

1. Name of the Student :
2. Name of the School :
3. Gender : Male [] Female []
4. Locality : Rural [] Urban []
5. Type of School : Government [] Private []
6. Type of Family : Joint [] Nuclear []
7. Type of Group : Arts [] Science []

INSTRUCTIONS

- There are some statement below. Each statement is followed by multiple choice i.e. Yes /No.
- Read each Statement carefully.
- After reading each statement mark your response in the appropriate column pitting at tick mark

S. NO	QUESTIONARIE	YES	NO
1	I like learning E-Learning.		
2	I will persist when facing difficulties in E-learning		
3	I like watch to E-Learning Videos		
4	I like reading Digital Contents		
5	I feel more confident in E-learning compared with my colleagues.		
6	I work on my Online assignments according to a planned schedule		
7	I study E-Learning diligently for potential development in the future		
8	In order to know the recent development in my major, I study E-Learning diligently		
9	E Learning is a very important tool for communication so I study it diligently		
10	In order to get an promotion in the future I use E-Learning diligently		
11	E- learning takes great advantage on the future work		
12	I treat Online examination as an evaluation of what I have learned about any subject.		
13	I like Online courses.		
14	I am excited when I have accomplished a difficult task in E-learning.		
15	I can finish my Online homework actively		
16	I study Online Course hard for the praise of the instructor.		
17	E-Learning helps me to improve my Teaching.		
18	My Colleagues always give lot of new information about E-Learning.		
19	My Colleagues encourage me to participate in E-Learning.		
20	I like Colleagues who have some sense of Knowledge through E-Learning.		

